

Lightning Nowcast on Airports in the Amazon Region Using Machine Learning

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Abstract— Lightning poses a potential threat to aircraft and the aviation industry in general, including airports. The lightning hotspots in the Brazilian Amazon region are located in the same regions as the most important airports. The Amazon region airports are vital for the rapid transport of humanitarian aid, especially to support indigenous territories. In this paper, we choose the Belem International Airport as a target place to predict lightning activity. The innovative approach uses solely grided lightning data as input features for lightning prediction. The approach relies on training a machine learning model (ResNet). Data from 2019 was used for training, and data from 2020 was used for testing, so the overall performance of the predictor is higher than 89%.

Keywords— Lightning nowcast, Lightning prediction, Machine Learning, Amazon airways, Amazon airports.

I. INTRODUCTION

Lightning presents a significant threat to aircraft and the aviation industry, including airports [1]. Modern aircraft are equipped with advanced lightning protection systems, including materials that conduct electricity, allowing lightning currents to pass over the aircraft's surface, preventing damage to the fuselage [2], [3]. Additionally, electronic systems are engineered to withstand the effects of lightning strikes. Redundant systems and shielding further mitigate risks, safeguarding critical flight instruments and communication systems. However, helicopters and smaller aircraft often lack such protection against lightning.

The Amazon region is one of the lightning hotspots in the world and has 697 private airfields that feature low-altitude flights, from which helicopters and smaller aircraft travel are vital for the rapid transport of humanitarian aid, especially to support indigenous territories. The combination of high

lightning rates and the need for small aircraft use is a concern for the Amazon community.

At the low-altitude airways in the Brazilian Amazon region, the lightning hotspots are located in the main airports of the region (Manaus and Belem) [4]; see Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Lightning density over low-altitude airways in the Brazilian Amazon region. Average for 2019-2022. Adapted from [4]

The Amazon weather is quite unstable, and can abruptly change to a severe thunderstorm, making it difficult for the pilot to see further, creating turbulence, and putting the passengers in danger.

Currently, the Geostationary Lightning Mapper (GLM) on board GOES 16, 17, and 18 can provide lightning data at near real-time resolution.

In [5] the authors presented an autoregressive approach to nowcast lightning for up to one hour, using solely lightning data

from GLM. Their setup used 500x500 matrices as training input, with pixels 10x10km in size, denoting the presence or absence of lighting activity in 15-minute intervals. When predicting 30 minutes ahead, they achieved recall equal to 73% and precision equal to 58%, using a significantly lower amount of data, compared to existing models in the literature.

Using meteorological data from ground stations of the National Institute of Meteorology as input to the prediction model, and Global Lightning Dataset (GLD 360) lightning occurrence records as ground truth, the authors in [6] employed a three-class Cascade Artificial Neural Network capable of predicting the presence of lightning activity in two severities (high and low) one hour ahead. They achieved 52% accuracy for the three-class model and 72% in the binary model.

Similarly, in [7] the authors achieved lightning prediction feeding a machine learning model with four commonly available meteorological parameters from MeteoSwiss single-site observations: air pressure at station level, air temperature, relative humidity, and wind speed. For prediction 30 minutes ahead, the authors observed a probability of detection value of 71%.

In [8] the authors employ a LightGBM model to predict lightning occurrence over the Contiguous United States. As inputs to the prediction model, they used GLM lightning records and Aerosol data from Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), as well as meteorological variables from CAMS, in a 0.25x0.25 grid and one-hour temporal level. They achieved 94.3% accuracy and a probability of detection equal to 75%.

In this work, we use solely GLM data as input for a machine-learning model that predicts lightning flashes over the main airport in the Amazon region.

II. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

A. Data

This work utilizes data from the Geostationary Lightning Mapper (GLM) to develop and train a Residual Neural Network (ResNet) model to nowcast lightning activity over the Val-de-Cans International Airport (BEL), located in the Amazon at 01° 23' 05" S 048° 28' 44" W.

The GLM is a high-speed optical sensor (500 frames per second) installed on the GOES 16, 17, and 18 satellites. It continuously records transient optical pulses at the 777.4 nm neutral oxygen emission line across the western hemisphere [9]. For this work, we utilize data exclusively from the GLM sensor aboard GOES-16, which encompasses the entire American continent, including the Amazon region. The spatial resolution ranges from approximately 8 km at the nadir to 14 km near the edges of the field of view. To be classified as a lightning event, an illuminated pixel must exceed a variable background difference threshold. Adjacent events occurring in the same frame are termed groups, and a lightning flash is defined as one

or more sequential groups separated by less than 330ms and 16.5 km. This study focuses solely on flash data.

The GLM dataset employed is structured in a 15x15 pixels grid, centered above BEL airport, as shown in Fig. 2. The pixels are 0.25°x0.25° wide and represent the flash density over this area.

Fig. 2 Area of study divided into a 15x15 pixels grid, centered above BEL airport, with pixels 0.25°x0.25° wide.

B. Preprocessing

The GLM data is processed into training and test subsets following the steps depicted in Fig. 3. At first, the data is resized into a 0.25°x0.25° grid, and then the data is cropped to encompass the area of study, leaving BEL airport in the center of the 15x15 pixels grid. The lightning in each pixel of the grid is counted in 10-minute intervals, creating a lightning density map for each time interval. This lightning density map is flattened to a 225 elements 1D vector, for ease of management during the training and testing phases of the model. The central pixel containing the lightning activity above BEL airport is assigned to be the truth value.

Fig. 3 Preprocessing steps for training and test subset generation.

The dataset consists of 9000 instances, in which 3,5% represents the presence of lightning activity. During the training process, this imbalance can lead to overfitting and results in non-optimal performance in the minority class, as the model does not learn from sufficient examples of the least represented class to pick up on the nuances of the task. To deal with this issue, we employ the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE). The SMOTE algorithm aims to introduce new artificial instances between k minority class nearest neighbors. It computes the difference of one feature vector to its nearest neighbors, randomly scales the values, and later adds the result to the original feature vector. In our training subset, the minority class (presence of lightning activity) was oversampled to the number of instances of the majority class (absence of lightning activity).

C. Algorithm

The prediction model employed in this study is the ResNet, short for Residual Neural Network. ResNets were devised to tackle the degradation problems encountered when expanding the number of layers in a network, by incorporating shortcut connections, which consist of linear layers bridging the input and output of each residual block. These connections allow the model to learn nuanced data patterns, thereby enhancing its ability to accurately predict complex information [10].

The ResNet model employed in this study follows the baseline presented in [10], [11], comprising 3 stacked residual blocks, each containing 3 convolutional blocks inside. Each residual block incorporates a linear layer connecting its input to its output. The convolutional blocks of the residual units work with kernel sizes of 8, 5, and 3, respectively, and corresponding filter sizes of 64, 128, and 128, as shown in Fig. 4. A Batch Normalization layer follows the chained convolutions to speed up and stabilize the convergence of the model, and the ReLU activation function is added to increase the non-linearity response. Then, the features are fed up to a Global Average Pooling layer to reduce the number of weights needed in the final Dense layer that gives the probabilities of each label using the softmax activation function.

Fig. 4 ResNet model structure

The input layer of the ResNet model consists of a 1D vector of the 225 pixels matrix, 30 minutes before the desired forecast. Predictions generated are binary, denoting either the presence (1) or absence (0) of lightning activity within the subsequent 30 minutes.

D. Training and Testing

To evaluate the generalization capabilities of the prediction model, we chose to use data from November 2019 as the train subset and data from November 2020 as the test subset. Fig. 5 shows the lightning activity for the area of study in November 2019, and Fig. 6 shows the lightning activity for the area of study in November 2020.

Fig. 5 Lightning activity for the area of study in November 2019.

Fig. 6 Lightning activity for the area of study in November 2020.

From the entire dataset, 50% of the samples were drawn to compose the training subset (November 2019) and the remaining 50% (November 2020) were used for testing. A total of 20% of the training subset was used as the validation subset. The Early Stopping callback in Keras was used to control the training epochs by monitoring the validation loss values, with a patience parameter equal to 50 epochs. The initial Learning Rate (LR) was set to 0.001 and was systematically reduced by employing the Reduce Learning Rate on Plateau Keras callback.

The LR is halved when a validation loss is identified, with a patience of 20 epochs. To save the best iteration of the model, we use the Model Checkpoint Keras callback, by monitoring the validation loss. These tools help to avoid overfitting and help save time in the training process.

Several metrics are commonly used to evaluate machine learning models, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F-score. Accuracy expresses the probability of a given instance being correctly predicted but lacks specific information regarding each class [12]. Precision denotes the ability to minimize false positives, and recall conveys the ability to minimize false negatives. Furthermore, the F-score is a composite measure and can be computed by the harmonic mean of recall and precision. In this paper, we evaluate the model by its macro-averaged precision, recall, and F-1 scores. Macro averaging is essential when dealing with an imbalanced testing dataset set, as it treats all classes equally [13], [14].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ResNet model achieved 88% and 90% recall scores for classes 0 and 1, respectively, as shown in the confusion matrix in Fig. 7. Class 0 achieved a 93% F1-score and class 1, 34%, which indicates an inferior precision score when predicting the presence of lightning activity. High recall and lower precision for class 1 suggest the model gives more importance to the prediction of the presence of lightning activity, even at the expense of occasional false positives.

Fig. 7 Confusion matrix for the prediction model. Class 0 stands for absence of lightning activity and class 1 stands for presence of lightning activity.

This behavior could prove invaluable in critical applications where it is important to identify all the positives. In this application, the model tends to overreport the prediction of positive lightning activity before and after its occurrence.

Fig. 8 shows the Receiver Operating Curves for both the presence and absence of lightning activity. The AUC value for both is above 0.95.

Fig. 8 Receiver Operating Curves for the prediction model. (a) Class 0 stands for the absence of lightning activity and (b) class 1 stands for the presence of lightning activity.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Lightning prediction solely based on satellite data can be a viable source of information to aid in making decisions in critical applications, such as in airports. This paper introduces a ResNet model capable of predicting lightning activity 30 minutes in advance, with satisfactory overall performance. The proposed methodology offers the potential to be expanded to all airways in the Brazilian Amazon region. The future goal of this study is to implement a more robust nowcast model, including other input features from geostationary satellites, over the low-altitude airways in the Amazon region to mitigate hazards to smaller aircraft.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported in part by the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq) grant 407250/2021-2.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Yair, "Lightning hazards to human societies in a changing climate," *Environmental Research Letters*, vol. 13, no. 12, p. 123002, Nov. 2018, doi: 10.1088/1748-9326/aaea86.
- [2] J. Pissolato, D. Thomas, C. Christopoulos, R. Callegari, and S. Nunes, "Current Density Distribution in Carbon Fiber Composites Following Lightning Strikes in Aircraft," in *International Conference on Lightning and Static Electricity*, Nagoya, 2017.
- [3] J. P. Filho, R. H. M. Callegari, R. de Araujo, and S. O. Nunes, "The Effects of Lightning Currents in Aircraft CFC Structures," *IEEE*

- Electromagn Compat Mag*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 62–69, 2021, doi: 10.1109/MEMC.2021.9400998.
- [4] A. F. R. Leal, L. C. Rocha, W. L. N. Matos, and M. N. G. Lopes, “Assessment of Lightning Occurrence on Airways and Waterways in the Amazon Region Using Satellite Data,” in *International Conference on Grounding & Lightning Physics and Effects*, Belo Horizonte, May 2023.
- [5] E. Mansouri, A. Mostajabi, C. Tong, M. Rubinstein, and F. Rachidi, “Lightning Nowcasting Using Solely Lightning Data,” *Atmosphere (Basel)*, vol. 14, no. 12, p. 1713, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.3390/atmos14121713.
- [6] W. L. N. Matos, A. F. R. Leal, and G. A. V. S. Ferreira, “A multiclass short-term lightning predictor for the Amazon region using ground-based meteorological data and artificial neural network,” *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 235, p. 110609, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.epr.2024.110609.
- [7] A. Mostajabi, D. L. Finney, M. Rubinstein, and F. Rachidi, “Nowcasting lightning occurrence from commonly available meteorological parameters using machine learning techniques,” *NPJ Clim Atmos Sci*, vol. 2, no. 1, p. 41, Nov. 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41612-019-0098-0.
- [8] G. Song, S. Li, and J. Xing, “Lightning nowcasting with aerosol-informed machine learning and satellite-enriched dataset,” *NPJ Clim Atmos Sci*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. 126, Aug. 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41612-023-00451-x.
- [9] S. J. Goodman *et al.*, “The GOES-R Geostationary Lightning Mapper (GLM),” *Atmos Res*, vol. 125–126, pp. 34–49, May 2013, doi: 10.1016/j.atmosres.2013.01.006.
- [10] Z. Wang, W. Yan, and T. Oates, “Time Series Classification from Scratch with Deep Learning Neural Networks: A Strong Baseline,” in *2017 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, Anchorage, May 2017, pp. 1578–1585.
- [11] A. F. R. Leal, G. A. V. S. Ferreira, and W. L. N. Matos, “Performance Analysis of Artificial Intelligence Approaches for LEMP Classification,” *Remote Sens (Basel)*, vol. 15, no. 24, p. 5635, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.3390/rs15245635.
- [12] M. Sokolova, N. Japkowicz, and S. Szpakowicz, “Beyond Accuracy, F-score and ROC: A Family of Discriminant Measures for Performance Evaluation,” Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer, 2006, pp. 1015–1021.
- [13] M. Sokolova and G. Lapalme, “A systematic analysis of performance measures for classification tasks,” *Inf Process Manag*, vol. 45, no. 4, pp. 427–437, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1016/j.ipm.2009.03.002.
- [14] K. Takahashi, K. Yamamoto, A. Kuchiba, and T. Koyama, “Confidence interval for micro-averaged F1 and macro-averaged F1 scores,” *Applied Intelligence*, vol. 52, no. 5, pp. 4961–4972, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10489-021-02635-5.